

***Phyllanthus emblica* mediated synthesis of palladium nanoparticles**

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Abstract : The immense catalytic property and affinity for hydrogen makes palladium nanoparticles very interesting in current scientific community. The general chemical methods in synthesizing palladium nanoparticles involves in the usage of costly and hazardous chemicals. The present single step synthesis method is a simple and environmental friendly green approach to generate large quantity of palladium nanoparticles using *Phyllanthus emblica* aqueous extract at room temperature without use of any surfactants or capping agents. The large contents of ascorbic acid and other polyphenols in plant extract acts both as reducing and capping agent. Thus synthesized nano-particles were characterized by UV-Vis, X-ray Diffraction Studies (XRD), Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) and Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM). The nanoparticles were in the size range of 25–100 nm and crystallized in cubic symmetry. FT-IR study revealed the capping of biomolecules on palladium nanoparticles which imparted its aerial stability.

Keywords : Palladium nanoparticles, *Phyllanthus emblica*, ascorbic acid, polyphenols.

Introduction

Palladium (Pd) is used in many areas of chemistry because of its good catalytic activity¹. The decrease in the particles size effectively increases catalyst activity of metal nanoparticles (NPs) due to its increased surface area². Palladium NPs were used in creating more efficient fuel cell catalyst and it is cheaper than other fuel cell catalyst like platinum and is more prolific³. Pd NPs were used as catalysts for hydrogenation reactions of many compounds such as unsaturated alcohols⁴, olefin and styrene⁵ and in many name reactions such as Heck reaction⁶, Stille coupling⁷, Suzuki reaction⁸ and C–N coupling⁹ reactions. There are many methods to synthesise stable Pd NPs^{10–14}. Some of them are sonochemical reduction of palladium nitrate¹⁰, reduction of Pd^{II} by alcohol¹¹, hydrazine reduction method¹², reduction using ascorbic acid¹³ and dimethylamine-borane reduction of Pd^{II} in supercritical carbon dioxide¹⁴. In general chemical synthetic techniques mostly use hazardous or toxic

reducing agents and surfactant/capping agents during the synthesis. A few green techniques that synthesise Pd NPs using coffee and tea extracts¹⁵, D-glucose¹⁶ and *Cinnamomum camphora* leaf extract¹⁷ after reducing Pd^{II} to Pd⁰ are reported recently. There is a great need to synthesise Pd NPs using non-toxic materials in a simple greener way to fulfil high demand in synthetic organic chemistry and renewable energy areas. *Phyllanthus emblica* (*P. emblica*) contains higher levels of ascorbic acid¹⁸, tannins and other polyphenols such as gallic acid and ellagic acid¹⁹. In addition, the polyphenols present in the aqueous extract are capable of taking part in redox type of reaction to yield ketones which donate electrons to facilitate the formation of metal NPs. This green and environmental benign technique addresses several key needs from green chemistry point of view such as avoiding toxic waste, usage of multifunctional materials and employing economically practicable method.

The objectives of the present study are to synthesise

Pd NPs using *P. emblica* aqueous extract and its characterisation.

Results and discussion

Out of many plants *P. emblica* was chosen for the reduction of Pd^{II} to Pd⁰ due to rich in water soluble ascorbic acid which acts as a good reducing agent¹⁸. Ascorbic acid contains both ketonic and hydroxyl groups. The mechanism of reduction may be explained using dehydro forms of phenolic acids as shown in Fig. 1. The reductant which is shown in Fig. 1, is confirmed using High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) (Fig. S1). This is a redox type of mechanism where phenolic acids are

Fig. 1. Schematic representation to demonstrate multi-functionality of *Phyllanthus emblica* extract in the formation of Pd nanoparticles.

emblica accelerates the formation of Pd NPs¹⁸.

The UV-Vis spectra of PdCl₂ solution (control), *P. emblica* aqueous extract and Pd NPs are shown in Fig. 2. Absorption peak at 425 nm is observed in the case of control indicating the existence of Pd^{II}. On interaction of *P. emblica* aqueous extract with PdCl₂ solution, the colour of the reaction mixture progressively was changed from transparent brownish yellow to deep brownish black within 15 min and the absorption peak at 425 nm disappeared with the appearance of a new peak at 275 nm which indicates the formation of Pd NPs. Usually Pd NPs appear near 230–240 nm in aqueous solution, but in the present study the band was observed at 275 nm. This red shift may be due to the capping of biomolecules on to the surface of metallic NPs. Similar shift in absorption band is observed for Pd NPs by Xu *et al.*¹⁶ where they used D-glucose for reducing Pd^{II} to Pd⁰. In the present study the effect of pH is carried out to check its morphological and size variations. 10 mL of extract is added to 2 mL of PdCl₂ of different pH solutions (2, 4, 6 and 8) and pH of the solution is measured in each case after completion of reduction. It is observed that the final pH was around 3.5 in all cases.

Fig. S1. HPLC chromatogram of aqueous *P. emblica* extract.

converted into its dehydro forms (oxidised form of polyphenols) with the generation of electrons. The high content of ascorbic acid (445 mg/100 g) present in *P.*

XRD pattern of Pd NPs is shown in Fig. 3. XRD pattern shows the major reflections at 40.11, 46.64, 68.06 and 81.76 which can be assigned to the planes (111),

Fig. 2. UV-Vis spectrum of Pd nanoparticles synthesised by green method.

Fig. 3. XRD pattern of the synthesised Pd nanoparticles.

(200), (220) and (311) of cubic Pd NPs and is in agreement with standard value (JCPDS No. 03-065-2867). Apart from the above reflections, a broad peak at lower angles is observed and this may arise due to the capping of oxidised phenols on the surface of Pd NPs.

Figs. 4a, 4b and 4c show the representative TEM images of Pd NPs at various magnifications. At lower magnification, finely dispersed pattern of Pd NPs is observed (Fig. 4a). The obtained colloidal Pd NPs are stable for 3 months without any aggregation. The particles seem to be almost spherical at lower magnification, but the anisotropic nature of NPs is evidenced at higher magnifications within the size ranging from 25–100 nm (Figs. 4a and 4c). The formation of anisotropic NPs may be due to

insufficiency of available bio-molecules which binds and restricts the growth of NPs²⁰. The spherical Pd NPs formed at the initial stages are stable because of sufficient oxidised bio-molecules containing carboxyl group (C=O) can co-ordinate with surface Pd atoms as shown in Fig. 1. But the particles formed later are less stable because of insufficiency of protective bio-molecules. These freshly formed nano crystals devoid of -C=O protecting groups are thermodynamically unstable²⁰. Because of room temperature sintering, assembly and rapid reduction process, these least stable spherical Pd NPs switch over the way to development of pentagonal and hexagonal shaped NPs²⁰. The polymeric type of material can be observed in TEM image as a black spot on the surface which is may be due to the presence of D-galacturonic acid in its polymeric form (pectin), a widely used gelling agent which is one of the constituents of *P. emblica*²⁰. The selected area electron diffraction pattern (SAED) reveals that the particles are polycrystalline in nature and the patterns are indexed as (111), (200), (220) and (311) reflection of cubic palladium NPs. Elemental analysis using EDS reveals the presence of palladium (Fig. 5b inset). The EDS results also reveal the presence of potassium in the synthesised Pd NPs. Potassium is vital to plant growth and is found in every plant cell. Among the minerals found in plants such as P, K, Ca, Mg and Fe, potassium is found in greater percentages in *P. emblica*²¹ which explains the presence of potassium in synthesised NPs. Peaks for copper appears due to the usage of Cu grids during the analysis.

Fig. 5 shows the FT-IR spectrum of *P. emblica* dried powder and bioinspired Pd NPs. FT-IR spectra of *P. emblica* dried powder shows IR bands at 1628.59 cm^{-1} and 1723.09 cm^{-1} which are characteristic of C=C and C=O stretching modes. Band at 1041.37 cm^{-1} corresponds to C-O stretching mode. The FT-IR spectra of Pd NPs shows bands at 1631.48 cm^{-1} and 1106.94 cm^{-1} which corresponds to C=O (hydrogen bonded) stretching and C-O stretching modes respectively, which confirms the capping of oxidised bio-molecules on Pd NPs. Also in EDS spectrum, the presence of carbon and oxygen is seen with Pd NPs. This may be due to the capping of elements of C and O on the surface of Pd NPs through some functional groups such as C=O and C=C. Generally polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP) is used to stabilize NPs and the stabilization occurs by co-ordination between C=O

Fig. 4. TEM images of Pd NPs : (a), (b) and (c) show TEM images of Pd nanoparticles at different magnifications and (d) shows the SAED pattern of Pd nanoparticles. Inset in (b) shows the EDAX pattern of palladium nanoparticles.

groups and Pd atoms^{10,11}. The strong interaction of carboxyl oxygen of oxidised bio-molecules and Pd core may be explained in terms of transfer of electron clouds around carboxyl oxygen from oxidised bio-molecules to the surface of Pd atoms at the interface as shown in Fig. 1²². So, the water soluble bio-molecules present in *P. emblica* may bind the surface through C=O to protect Pd NPs from oxidation.

Uses of various green sources in production of Pd NPs are shown in Table 1. Although the green techniques like sonochemical¹⁰, UV irradiation²³ and L-ascorbic acid^{13,24} method to synthesise Pd NPs are known in literature, these methods use certain stabilizer like PVP¹⁰ and carboxy methyl cellulose (CMC)²⁴. In addition, some plant based synthesis of Pd NPs are reported, but in many cases either the reduction time or the reaction temperatures was high (Table 1). Data on Table 1 shows that *Curcuma longa* tuber mediated synthesis required 72 h to prepare Pd NPs at 30 °C²⁵, *Cinnamomum camphora* leaf extract required 12 h for reduction at 30 °C¹⁷ and a

similar plant based method using banana peel extract required only just 3 min at 80 °C²⁶. The present study using *Phyllanthus emblica* is able to produce anisotropic Pd NPs in 15 min at RT (29 ± 2 °C). So the present method can synthesise Pd NPs in a lesser time. The presence of other polyphenols like kaempferol, gallic acid, ellagic acid may enhance the formation of Pd NPs faster at room temperature in the present study. More studies are necessary to proof polyphenol selective formation of Pd NPs followed by its stabilization.

Experimental

Reagents and materials :

P. emblica was purchased from local market and PdCl₂ (assay : 99%) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich, CA. Absolute ethanol (99.9% pure) and double distilled water were used throughout the study. All other reagents used were of analytical reagent grade.

Preparation of *Phyllanthus emblica* extract :

Aqueous extract of *P. emblica* was prepared by boil-

Fig. 5. (a) FT-IR spectrum of *Phyllanthus emblica* dried powder and (b) FT-IR spectrum of synthesised Pd nanoparticles.

Table 1. Various green sources used in recent years for the production of Pd nanoparticles

Sr. No.	Green source for reduction of Pd ^{II} to Pd ⁰	Reduction time	Reaction temperature (°C)	Avg. particle size (nm)	Shape of particles	Reference
1.	<i>Curcuma longa</i> tuber	72 h	30	10–15	Spherical	23
2.	L-Ascorbic acid/CMC stabilizer	24 h	95	3.6	Spherical	22
3.	Sonochemical/PVP/ethylene glycol	3 h	–	5–20	Spherical	10
4.	UV irradiation/K ₂ C ₂ O ₄	5 min	–	15–125	Anisotropic	21
5.	Banana peel	3 min	80	50	–	24
6.	Coffee/tea	–	RT	5–100	Spherical	15 ^b
7.	<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i> leaf	12 h	30	3.6–9.9	Spherical	17
8.	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	15 min	RT	25–100	Anisotropic	– ^a

^aPresent study, RT - Room temperature (29 ± 2 °C). ^bRT not mentioned.

ing 2.0 g of the finely grinded powder of *P. emblica* in 100 mL of double distilled water in a temperature controlled water bath for an hour at 100 °C, cooled to room temperature and filtered through 0.2 µm cellulose nitrate

membrane filter paper. The filtrate was used directly for the synthesis of NPs.

Synthesis of Pd NPs :

2 mL of palladium chloride solution (0.01 M) was

added to 10 mL aqueous extract of *P. emblica* and mixed thoroughly. After 15 min of settling the mixture was centrifuged at 15000 rpm for 15 min and separated out the solid nanomaterials. Again the solid NPs were dispersed in absolute ethanol, centrifuged and filtered. This washing process was repeated thrice and then purified Pd NPs were stored in a dust free container.

Characterization of Pd NPs :

UV-Visible spectroscopy study :

Preliminary characterization of Pd NPs was carried out using UV-Visible spectroscopy (Jasco V-670 UV-Vis spectrophotometer). The reduction process was monitored by measuring absorbance of 10 fold diluted sample using deionised water. Deionised water was used also as a blank. The spectral data recorded were then plotted using Origin 6.1.

X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) study :

Purified Pd NPs were subjected to X-ray diffraction analysis (Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with Cu K α radiation, $\lambda = 1.54 \text{ \AA}$). Prior to the analysis, the instrument was calibrated using lanthanum hexaboride (LaB6). The scanning range was done between 10° and 90°.

measurement (JASCO FT-IR 4100) in the diffuse reflectance mode at a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ in KBr pellets. Pure untreated dry *P. emblica* seed powder was pelletized and used as a control under the same instrumental conditions for quality check with Pd NPs.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) study :

The size and morphology of the synthesized Pd NPs were determined by High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) (JEOL JEM 2100 High Resolution Transmission Electron Microscope). The sample was prepared for TEM study as follows. 1 mL of the reaction mixture containing Pd NPs was diluted to 5 mL and sonicated using ultrasonic bath for 5 min. Afterwards a drop of it was placed Cu grid with ultrathin Cu on holey C film and allowed to dry it in vacuum. The instrument was operated with an acceleration voltage of 200 KV. Elemental composition of Pd NPs was obtained from EDS study (Fig. S2). Spectrum was recorded at selected areas on the solid surface of Pd NPs using an EDS instrument coupled with HR-TEM (Carl Zeiss, EVO MA 15, Oxford Instrument).

Fig. S2. EDAX spectrum of Pd nanoparticles.

Fourier Transformed Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) study :

Purified Pd NPs were analysed by FT-IR spectral

Conclusions

A green and environmental benign approach is demonstrated to synthesise Pd NPs within a size range of 25–

100 nm using *P. emblica* aqueous extract at room temperature. The ascorbic acid rich *P. emblica* aqueous extract was responsible for the reduction of Pd^{II} to Pd⁰. FT-IR study confirmed the presence of bio-molecules capped on the surface of Pd NPs. This is a faster low cost approach to synthesise Pd NPs which could be used in various catalytic applications and renewable energy areas.

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